

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D7.2 Quality Assurance Risk Management plan

WP7- Project Management

Version: 1.0

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Executive Summary

The CALIPER Quality Assurance and Risk Management report acts as a reference about the overall project management procedures that will be followed by all partners, during the whole project duration in order to:

- Ensure a high quality of the project activities and results
- Ensure that deliverables are developed according to high quality standards
- Define quality objectives and standards
- Develop specific performance indicators

In terms of Quality Assurance, the reports defined the roles and responsibilities of all project partners, the relevant processes they face to follow, and the Key Performance Indicators they have to follow in order to secure high quality on the project results.

Complementary, with regards to the Risk Management, it defines the approach to identify and manage potential risks, as well as presents the list of the current identified risks.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This deliverable describes the quality assurance and risk management procedures that should be performed in the CALIPER project. This deliverable defines a consistent plan and set of procedures to guarantee that quality aspects of the project are met and regularly monitored. In addition, it outlines the procedures for identifying and handling risks and causes of project deviations. The project Coordinator is applying the procedures that has already adopted in the several H2020 projects that has Coordinated before, with successful results, and is updating them continuously.

The quality assurance and risk management procedures presented in this document are applicable to all the activities of the project. Hence, compliance to these procedures is mandatory for all partners.

1.2 Indented audience

This document is a key reference for the following:

- the Project Coordinator and the Quality and Risk Manager
- all consortium members
- any other person who will join the partner's working teams at a later stage.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

Chapter two (2) presents the CALIPER quality control, including the different management roles, the monitoring of the daily performance management and the quality standards for the deliverables and procedures. Then follows Chapter three (3) that outlines the risk management overall approach, the partner roles and responsibilities, as well as the potential risks.

1.4 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The Quality Assurance – Risk Management plan applies horizontally and equally at all the project WPs.

2 Project quality control

Integral part of the project management plan is the quality assurance procedures should provide the solid ground for successful, timely and quality implementation of the project activities. The quality management procedures defined in this deliverable form a common standard to be applied and followed throughout the entire project lifetime. Therefore, the main purpose of this report is to define a consistent set of procedures, processes and guidelines in order to ensure high quality standards of the project outcomes. The quality assurance procedures defined in this document focus on:

- **Performance management:** Assessing the progress of the work on a regular basis
- **Communication Management:** Managing the interaction between partners during the work execution
- **Documents / deliverables management:** Defining how and when the documentation and the deliverables have to be exchanged by the partners and submitted to the European Commission

2.1 Quality management roles

All the consortium partners have mutual and equal responsibility to produce high quality deliverables and project outcomes.

The **Risk and Quality manager**, member of the Project Management Team (see D7.1) is responsible for ensuring the project's quality aspect, applying the following duties:

- Maintain the quality assurance procedures with the support of a representative from each partner.
- Act as a focal point for quality issues and liaise with partners to ensure that an appropriate level of quality is maintained for each element of the project.
- Ensure that activities and reports are completed to an adequate quality and in a timely manner.
- Monitor and audit the project activities for conformance with the project plans, in particular performing milestone reviews of contractual deliverables.
- Initiate action to prevent the occurrence of any non-conformity.

All **WP Leaders** should assist the Risk and Quality manager and shall therefore ensure:

- To adhere to the quality assurance procedures adequately, and
- To immediately inform the Risk and Quality manager of any problems related to quality assurance.

The Risk and Quality manager should be assisted also by:

- The **Scientific/GEP Manager** to ensure the scientific quality and propose improvements when necessary
- The **RRI manager** to ensure that the rules on responsive research innovation and adequately applied.

2.2 Performance management

Performance management is about the management of partner's performance in relation to the project milestones and objectives. The key tool to monitor the project progress and how performance is deviating from the plan, is the project Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These are defined already within the Grand Agreement. However, during the project progress these Indicators are continuously evaluated and updated according to the real project implementation circumstances, cost and schedule.

The project indicators will be continuously monitored throughout the project progress and will be evaluated at a frequent basis: (i) every six months within the internal and official project reporting, among the consortium (ii) the results of performance measurement and evaluation (indicators and their values) will be part of the progress reporting to the European Commission, therefore every 18 months during the technical review, any adaptations will be discussed between the consortium and the European Commission. The content of such reports is described at the Chapter 2.4 'Monitoring and reporting procedure' of the D7.1 Project Management Handbook. The project Coordinator is in charge to preparing the reports and ask each partner for any additional contributions.

In addition, the Coordinator organizes **monthly online meetings** in which the Work Package briefly report the progress to ensure the early identification of deviations from the planned project targets including delays or early finishes and their implications on the overall progress.

The indicator targets set by CALIPER in the Grand Agreement define its level of ambition, help to monitor progress throughout implementation and allow saying at the end of the project whether the objectives have been achieved.

All indicators under CALIPER are expressed in quantity (such as 'the number of', 'percentage of') in order to be able to measure results and outputs objectively, but they need to be completed by qualitative aspects (such as addressed target groups, in which place the change is produced).

To set a good indicator system at a project level, the indicators should also be smart, which means:

- **Specific:** is it clear what exactly will be measured, in what geographical area measurements will be made, what units etc.
- **Measurable:** will the project be able to collect accurate information to measure progress towards the targets set? The information required for measurements should be quite easy to collect. It should be aware that different regions and countries collect data in different ways, thus all partners should be able to monitor and report on the indicators selected.
- **Achievable:** closely linked to identifying what changes are anticipated as a result of the project work and whether the results planned are realistic.
- **Relevant:** will the indicators measure all of the project's key activities?
- **Timed:** stating when something should happen (e.g. increase in visitor numbers by the end of the project).

The tables below depict the main project's indicators to meet the project objectives and the envisioned expected impact, as they have been defined within the Grand Agreement. Each table includes the description of the indicators, the target value and the linked WP(s). **The indicators are monitored also online** through the Teamwork Project Management Tool, to secure transparency among all consortium members and availability of information.

Objective 1: To assess the existing external and internal conditions that influence gender equality in order to foster informed context-sensitive design of GEPs and ensure their applicability					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
Stakeholders reached for the implementation of the external assessment	1	M1-M8	D1.3	#of stakeholders	100
Number of top management decision makers interviewed: at least 5 at each RPO/RFO	1	M1-M8	D1.2	# of decision makers interviewed	45
Number of middle managers interviewed: at least 3 at each RPO/RFO	1	M1-M8	D1.2	# of middle managers interviewed	27
Number of members of the 9 RPO/RFO communities, including students, professors, administrative staff and several gender experts that will be actively involved in internal consultations	1	M1-M8	D1.2	# of members involved in internal consultations	650
Training sessions to guide the GEP Working Groups about how to conduct the internal assessment: 1 face to face training session at each RPO/RFO.	1	M1-M8	D1.2	# of training sessions	9
Implementation of internal assessments: 1 at each RPO/RFO.	1	M1-M8	D1.2	# of internal assessments	9

Table 1: Objective 1 Key Performance Indicators

Objective 2: Support partnering RPOs/RFO in designing and developing GEPs through motivation, awareness and knowledge transfer					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
Establishment GEP Working Groups	1	D1.2	M1-6	#GEP Working Groups (Target 9 (1 per RPO/RFO))	9
Identify best practices showing the dynamics of promoting equality as a driver of quality and excellence of research and innovation with a multi-	1	D1.3	M1-M8	# of best practices promoting equality as a	15

stakeholder and quadruple helix approach in regional ecosystems				driver of quality and excellence of research (Target> 15)	
Interviews with experts/stakeholders on implementing organizational/ institutional gender equality policies leveraging on collaboration and alignment with other actors within innovation ecosystems	1	D1.2/D1.3	M2-M8	#of interviews (minimum of 20)	20
Individual customized and face to face training session in national languages targeted at WGs	1	D1.2	M2-M6	# training sessions 9 (1 per RPO/RFO)	9
Internal Workshops at each RPOs/RFOs run by GEP Working Groups where the results of T1.3 and 1.4 will be further discussed so as to understand the potentials and barriers	5	D5.3	M20-M21	#Internal Workshops (9 (1 per RPO/RFO))	9
Online training sessions: this activity will provide additional content to support the GEP Working Groups, 3 rounds	5	D5.3/D5.6	M16/M18/M36	#Online training sessions (3 rounds)	3
Multi-stakeholder dialogues part of co-design process	2	D2.2	M11-M13	#Workshops organised for multi stakeholder dialogs 18 (2 per RPO/RFO)	18

Table 2: Objective 2 Key Performance Indicators

Objective 3: To ensure an efficient tailored implementation and refinement of the GEPs					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
Round of iterations and refinements of GEPs	3	D3.2/D3.3	M16-M44	# iteration rounds	2
Number of different stakeholders involved in the implementation process in each RPO/RFO	3	D3.1/D3.2/D3.3	M16-M44	#of categories representing different research, academic, management,	10

				administrative staff (at least 10)	
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Table 3: Objective 3 Key Performance Indicators

Objective 4: To assess the GEPs' effectiveness and evaluate project achievements beyond the consortium					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
Appointment of one staff member at each RPO/RFO as internal contact person for the evaluation to safeguard the formative approach	4	D4.2	M6-M44	#of internal contact person (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	9
Upgraded reports for each evaluation including recommendations and guidelines for refinement of the Gender Equality Action Plans	4	D4.2/D4.3	M6-M44	# of reports	2
Formative evaluation webinars to share results from the reports with the GEPs teams	4	D4.2/D4.3	M10-M44	# of webinars (total 18: 2 per RPO/RFO)	18
Summative evaluation on site visits at each partner institution	4	D4.4	M10-M44	# of on site visits (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	9
Dedicated sessions to monitoring and evaluation within steering committee meetings	4	D4.2/D4.3	M10-M44	# of sessions within steering committee meetings (> 4)	4
% of the indicators included in the evaluation methodology met by the end of the project	4	D4.4	M10-M44	# of indicators met by the end of the project (> 70%)	70%

Table 4: Objective 4 Key Performance Indicators

Objective 5: Ensure the sustainability and expansion of the GEPs at a national and international level by targeting key stakeholders					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
% of the piloted actions of the GEPs institutionalized and integrated into permanent measures and procedures, official strategic documents and	2,3,5	D5.4	M9-M48	% of the GEP actions	70

regulations of the involved RPOs/RFOs by the end of the project				institutionalized (> 70)	
Number of GE webinars targeting external RPOs/RFOs	5	D5.3/D5.6	M20-M48	# of webinars (Task 5.2) (Total 18 (2 per RPO/RFO))	18
Number of RPOs/RFOs engaged and influenced by the project to initiate their own GEPs	5	D5.3/D5.6	M1-M48	# engaged RPOs/RFOs (>80)	80
Number of RPOs/RFOs endorsing the CALIPER Charter on Institutional Change for Gender Equal Research and Innovation Hubs	5	D5.5	M20-M48	# of RPOs/RFOs endorsing the CALIPER Charter	40
Number of actors/ stakeholders involved within the CALIPER Research and Innovation Hub actively collaborating with the 9 participating RPOs/RFOs in specific GEPs' implementation actions	3, 5	D5.3/D5.6	M16-M44	# of Research and Innovation Hub actors/ stakeholders involved within the GEP implementation (> 100 R&I actors)	100
FemTech events to raise awareness on STEM related research organised by RPOs attracting more than 400 participating female students and researchers.	5	D5.3/D5.6	M23	# of participating female students and researchers at FemTech events (Total 9 (1 per RPO/RFO))	400
Number of policy briefings at national and European level	6	D6.5/D6.6/D6.8	M12-M48	# of policy briefings (10 per year (9 national and 1 EU))	30
Number of policy makers engaged throughout the project	6	D6.2/D6.3/D6.4	M1-M48	# policy makers engaged throughout the project (>40)	40

Table 5: Objective 5 Key Performance Indicators

Objective 6: Increase the societal relevance of scientific knowledge, technologies and innovations and have a strong social impact					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
Number of new linkages developed within each innovation ecosystem of the partnering RPOs and RFOs	2	D5.3/D5.6	M1-M48	#new linkages developed	50
Number of multi-stakeholder dialogues in each pilot, multi-stakeholder dialogue workshops at each RPO/RFO	2	D2.2	M11-M13	#Workshops organised for multi stakeholder dialogs 18 (2 per RPO/RFO)	18
Number of attendees in the local multi-stakeholder dialogues	2	D2.2	M11-M13	>25 participants at each workshop	225

Table 6: Objective 6 Key Performance Indicators

Expected impact: Increase the number of research organisations and higher education establishments implementing gender equality plans					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
RPOs/RFOs design and implement GEP and shared in the GEAR tool	2,3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# GEPs (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	9
Change internal procedures, regulations, services	3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# GEPs (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	27
Develop strategic documents	3	D3.4	M9-M44	# GEPs (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	9
At least 80 external RPOs and RFOs will participate in the awareness-raising webinars to introduce the Caliper Charter.	5	D5.3/D5.6	M20-M48	# of external RFOs/RPOs	80
Organise final conference, 80 individuals from min 15 RPOs, 8 RFOs and other stakeholders such as gender equality experts, professional associations, policy makers will participate in the final conference	6	D6.4	M44-M48	# of individuals	80
Number of RPOs/RFOs engaged and influenced by the project to initiate their own GEPs	5	D5.3/D5.6	M1-M48	# engaged RPOs/RFOs (>80)	80

Number of RPOs/RFOs endorsing the CALIPER Charter on Institutional Change for Gender Equal Research and Innovation Hubs	5	D5.5	M20-M48	# of RPOs/RFOs endorsing the CALIPER Charter	40
Number of actors/ stakeholders involved within the CALIPER Research and Innovation Hub actively collaborating with the 9 participating RPOs/RFOs in specific GEPs' implementation actions	3, 5	D5.3/D5.6	M16-M44	# of Research and Innovation Hub actors/ stakeholders involved within the GEP implementation (> 100 R&I actors)	100

Table 7: Expected impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Expected impact: Increase the participation of women in research and innovation and improvement of their career's prospects					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
PROs/RFOs develop concrete GEPs actions for supporting female researchers progressing in their careers	3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# actions (at least 2 at each RPO)	18
RPOs/RFOs develop actions for preventing and contrasting gender bias in selection and recruitment procedures including actions undertaken via synergies with the R&I Hubs	3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# actions (at least 1 at each RPO)	15
Number of collaborative actions (Research/industry/government/civil society) included in the GEPs within the Caliper R&I Hubs to attract more girls to STEM.	2	D2.2	M11-M13	#Workshops organised for multi stakeholder dialogs 18 (2 per RPO/RFO)	18
External RPOs/RFOs adopt actions to prevent and contrast gender bias in attracting more female students to STEM studies and careers	5	D5.3/D5.6	M20-M48	# external RPOs/RFOs	20
New stable events/initiatives organized to attract girls to STEM studies	5	D5.3/D5.6	M1-M48	# events (1 each RPO/RFO)	9
RFOs adopt new procedures for the evaluation of research projects	3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# procedures	2

Table 8: Expected impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Expected impact: Improve gender balance in decision-making bodies in research organisations					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
9 GEPs including specific actions on gender equality in decision making process aiming at structural changes to raise the female presence in decision making bodies.	2,3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# GEPs including the specific actions (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	9
Internal workshops with GEPs working groups	1	D1.2	M1-M8	# of training sessions	9
3 rounds of online training sessions in each GEP Working Group	5	D5.3/D5.6	M16/M18/M36	#Online training sessions (3 rounds)	3
Middle managers/high level managers among attendants to GEPs workshops/training workshops and webinars	1,5	D1.2/D5.3/D5.6	M1-M36	% Middle managers/high level managers among attendants (Target 10-15%)	15%
Promotional videos to reach at least 600 researchers and academics	6	D6.2/D6.3/D6.4	M3-M48	# of views (at least 600)	600

Table 9: Expected impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Expected impact: Inclusion of the gender dimension in research content and increase in the quality and societal relevance of produced knowledge, technologies and innovations					
Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
7 GEPs including dedicated measures to review existing research programmes to take gender into consideration as a dimension in research content	2,3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# GEPs including the specific actions (total 9: 1 per RPO/RFO)	7
RPOs include in the GEP dedicated measures to review existing	2,3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	% of existing programmes	30%

research programmes to take gender into consideration as a dimension in research content				to be reviewed	
RPOs rate the new research programmes taking the gender dimension into account across the research cycle	2,3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	% of new research programmes rated	50%
RPOs include 1 new module or course on gender as a research dimension in STEM	2,3	D2.3, D3.4	M9-M44	# of RPOs including a module or course	7
Training/raising awareness workshops and sessions should cover specific issues of gender in research content	D5.3/D5.6	M16/M18/M36	#Online training sessions (3 rounds)	Online Training sessions	70%

Table 10: Expected impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Expected impact: The GEPs will contribute to the achievement of the ERA objectives: (in the medium to long term)

- Remove barriers to the recruitment
- Retention and career progression of female researchers
- Address gender imbalances in decision making processes
- Strengthen the gender dimension in research programmes

Performance Indicators	WPs	Deliverables	Duration	Measurement type	Target Value
Develop policy briefings per year	6	D6.5/D6.6/D6.8	M12-M48	# of policy briefings (10 per year (9 national and 1 EU))	30
Establish synergies with relevant projects	6	D6.2/D6.3/D6.4	M3-M48	# of projects established synergy	10
Number of Ministries for Research, Education and Innovation in the MS represented in the consortium actively engaged in R&I Hubs at different stages of the CALIPER project, to contribute to GEPs development, implementation and/or sustainability and dissemination	6	D6.2/D6.3/D6.4	M1-M48	# ministries engaged throughout the project	9

Number of GEPs implementation scenarios designed	2	D2.1	M9-M11	# implementation scenarios (3 per each RPO/RFO)	27
RPOs/RFOs organise dialogue workshops to identify key challenges	2	D2.2	M11-M13	#Workshops organised for multi stakeholder dialogs 18 (2 per RPO/RFO)	18

Table 11 Expected impact Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

2.3 Quality Standards that apply to deliverables and procedures

During the CALIPER project implementation, a number of project outcomes will be made. All these deliveries should adhere to certain quality standards. Each of these deliveries should be validated and verified before delivering to the EC. Without standards and procedures, the risk is that team members will complete their work with different understandings of the procedures they are required to follow and the results they are intended to produce, resulting in productivity losses, quality losses and schedule delays.

The development of standards and procedures is an iterative process. Thus, the standards and procedures are never complete but can expect to evolve and be enhanced as the project proceeds. As the procedures are put in place and implemented, during the project progress improvements will be identified and introduced under the control of the Quality Manager.

The project deliveries can be generally categorized as documents and reports (Public Deliverables, Progress reports, GEPs, Policy Briefings, Scientific publications), events (final conference, trainings), and online webinars (trainings). All project deliveries will be published centrally by the [project website](#). It has been set up in order to attract large number of target groups and the broad general public. They will be able to find regularly updated information about the project, its progress, contact information, project achievements and results.

2.3.1 Quality of events and online webinars

All events planned within the project need to be professionally organized. The host organisation will be responsible for providing the smooth realization of the event, which includes all necessary arrangements and coordination, preparation of invitation packages (invitation letters, agendas, etc), details on location /online tool, available accommodation and travel arrangements, etc.

The deadline for completing necessary preparation activities depends on the event itself, but it must provide enough time for participants' registration and travel preparations.

Additionally, the host organisation will be responsible for provision of all materials required for the event (promotional or informative material, supporting documents, printed agendas, etc), as well as for the elaboration of reports/minutes on the held event upon its completion.

Every planned event within the CALIPER project must also meet the requirements regarding the structure and the number of target audience.

All the material used for the organisation and implementation of such events should have the CALIPER project brand. All templates with the project logo have been prepared and these are described at D6.1 CALIPER Dissemination Strategy.

2.3.2 Project documents and deliverables

The official CALIPER deliverables and milestones need to be submitted and approved by the EC. These should be aligned with the Grant Agreement. Any discrepancy between actual and planned achievements needs to be explained and justified. Official deliverables and milestones go through the quality control by peer review before being published. It should be noted that in order to ensure that official deliverables and milestones are met, all project partners and particularly work package leaders will develop the work plan in more detail. This should be done by adding internal and more specific activities, tasks, and milestones into the work plan.

In order to prevent issues for the decoding on the documents, it is recommended to use the following tools: Word processing: MS Word, Spreadsheet: MS Excel, Slides presentation: MS PowerPoint, Document for web publication: PDF.

2.3.2.1 Deliverables and data control

Every deliverable should be carefully composed with rich content, a clear and unified structure and a professional presentation. In order to achieve this, the report should be based on the following criteria:

Content

The content of each deliverable report depends on the type of deliverable itself. It should cover all the information relevant to the task that it refers to. As a general principle, this is the responsibility of its author(s). Nevertheless, the reports should meet a set of requirements, based on the following aspects:

- **Completeness.** Information provided in the deliverable report must be reliable, complete and supported by relevant references.
- **Relevance.** Presented information should be relevant for the achievement of the corresponding goals
- **Accuracy.** Information presented should be focused on the key issues.
- **Language features.** Before elaboration of the final version, the report should be submitted for proof reading.

Appearance and structure

The deliverable reports should have a uniformed appearance, structure and referencing scheme. It is therefore necessary to use the document referencing and template already provided.

Rules for deliverables – File naming

CALIPER has set rules below for the filenames to keep consistency.

File Name: INTR_ORIG_DT_ (Name)_VER

INTR: Internal reference (PROJ, WPxy)

ORIG = Originator. This is the acronym of the author organization.

DT - Document Type. Possible values:

- Dxyz: Deliverable e.g. D012, D231
- (F)Pxy: (Financial) Periodic Progress Report e.g. FP01, etc.
- FCxy: Financial Cost Statement e.g. CS01, CS02 etc.
- MAxy: Agenda e.g. MA01, MA02 etc.
- MMxy: Meeting Minutes e.g. MM01, MM02 etc.
- MPxy: Meeting Presentation e.g. MP01, MP02 etc.
- RVxy: Review Presentation e.g. RV01, RV02.
- LTxy: Letter or any other Document, Report etc.

VER = Version: 0.X for drafts, 1.X for Final versions and 2.X submitted after review X=01,02,03.... Subsequent versions of the same document.

Example: CALIPER_VIL_D7.1_Quality Assurance–Risk Management plan_0.1.doc

2.3.2.2 Deliverables review procedure

Quality review of deliverables within the CALIPER project will be realized at three levels:

- **1st level control:** The main author circulated the template to all partners for comments, 8 weeks before the deadline
- **2nd level control:** The main author prepares the Deliverable and provided it to partners assigned for review, 3 weeks before the deadline. Within five (5) working days from deliverable draft receipt, those reviewers should send back their review results, suggestions and recommendations for improvements using the review report template (Annex 1). The final rating of the Deliverable draft can be marked as:
 - fully accepted - In case the deliverable is fully accepted by all reviewers, it can be considered the final version, and/or sent to the next level of revision (if necessary).
 - revisions required - The deliverable author has five (5) working days to include or disregard those comments and finalize the deliverable.
 - rejected – Non-conformance plan needs to be applied.

In case profound disagreements between reviewers and author, the deliverable will have to go through the next level of control.

- **3rd level control:** The main author integrates the comments into a second draft and deliver it to the partners assigned for review, 1-2 week before the deadline
- **4th level control:** The main author delivers the final version to the Coordinator and Quality manager, 1 week before the deadline

2.3.2.3 Deliverables review assignment

Each deliverable will be reviewed by the appointed members of the Project Management Team (at least two), each of them not working in the institutes of the partners involved in preparing the deliverable.

Del. No	Deliverable name	WP	Lead participant	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Delivery date	Delivery date
D7.3	Data management and RRI plan	7	VIL	UEFISCI	YU	M5	May 2020

D5.1	Engagement and change management strategy	5	ULB	VIL	STU BA	M6	June 2020
D1.2	Internal Gender Equality Assessments Results	1	VIL	SV	UEFISCI	M8	Aug 2020
D1.3	Gender analysis of research and innovation ecosystems and reports from the local R&I Hubs	1	SV	VIL	SRNSF	M8	Aug 2020
D4.1	Formative Evaluation methodology	4	SV	VIL	UZG	M9	Sept 2020
D8.1	H- Requirement No1	8	VIL	UNILE	YU	M9	Sept 2020
D8.2	POPD - Requirement No. 2	8	VIL	YU	SRNSF	M9	Sept 2020
D2.1	Co-design guidelines for the development and reporting of scenarios	2	ULB	SV	NTUA	M11	Nov 2020
D2.2	Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues	2	ULB	SV	UZG	M13	Jan 2021
D2.3	GEPs	2	SV	ULB	SRNSF	M15	Mar 2021
D6.2	Dissemination and communication activities v.1	6	VIL	YAE	STU BA	M15	Mar 2021
D5.2	Report on existing identified opportunities of facilitating the engagement and access to the market of STEM researchers	5	VIL	ULB	YAE	M18	June 2021
D5.3	Engagement activities reporting v1	5	STU BA	YAE	VIL	M24	Dec 2021
D6.5	Policy Briefings v1	6	VIL	ULB	SV	M24	Dec 2021

D3.1	GEPs implementation during phase 1	3	UZG	VIL	SV	M28	April 2022
D3.2	Mini reports on the redesign and refinement elements in each RPO/ RFO v1	3	IRB	UZG	VIL	M29	May 2022
D4.2	Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 1	4	SV	VIL	IRB	M29	May 2022
D6.3	Dissemination and communication activities v.2	6	VIL	YAE	STU BA	M30	June 2022
D5.4	Sustainability and Expansion Plan	5	VIL	SV	ULB	M35	Nov 2022
D6.6	Policy Briefings v2	6	VIL	ULB	SV	M36	Dec 2022
D6.7	Role models' report	6	YAE	VIL	SV	M40	April 2023
D3.3	Mini reports on the redesign and refinement elements in each RPO/ RFO v2	3	IRB	UZG	SV	M43	July 2023
D3.4	Final GEPs	3	VIL	SV	UZG	M44	Aug 2023
D4.3	Interim Formative Evaluation Report – phase 2	4	SV	VIL	YAE	M44	Aug 2023
D4.4	Summative Evaluation Results	4	SV	VIL	YAE	M44	Aug 2023
D5.5	CALIPER Charter	5	SV	VIL	STU BA	M48	Dec 2023
D5.6	Engagement activities reporting v2	5	STU BA	YAE	VIL	M48	Dec 2023
D6.4	Dissemination and communication activities v.3	6	VIL	YAE	STU BA	M48	Dec 2023
D6.8	Policy Briefings v3	6	VIL	ULB	SV	M48	Dec 2023

Table 12: Deliverables review assignment

3 Risk management

Within the CALIPER project twelve organisations from different European countries will work together following the work plan, towards the common scope to reach their common goal, to improve the gender equality in their institutions and link activities with the innovation. To secure that the strategic direction, the operational management, the results and the budget of the project remain on track, the risk management is a high priority. The risk management scope is to establish processes and methods to assess and mitigate risks via an anticipatory approach.

3.1 Risk management approach

The risk management takes place through four core different stages:

- a) **Risk identification:** involves the identification of a risk
- b) **Analysis:** the assessment of risk importance
- c) **Monitoring:** continuous check of the progress
- d) **Management:** the evaluation of whether the risk level/impact is higher than the risk that could be accepted for the project

In case that a risk exceeds the acceptable levels, a risk analysis activity will be instantiated that will define the required actions in order to set the risk within acceptable levels. In addition, the management of risks involves the planning of contingency actions, the redistribution of resources, the evaluation of the results, as well as ensuring the stability of the new status.

3.2 Risk management roles and responsibilities

The responsible person for CALIPER is the Coordinator and Quality manager. Her main obligation is to identify, monitor, and handle internal and external risks and inform all (or directly involved) partners when necessary. At the level of risk identification, the WP leaders play an important key role to communicate with the Coordinator any upcoming risk they foresee. On a monthly basis, the consortium meets online and WP leaders are expected to present the progress and achievements of their WP, as well as an assessment of risks that may hinder progress and propose contingency plans where necessary to address any specific identified risks.

In particular, the types of risks that may emerge in a project like CALIPER fall into the following categories:

- **Operational risks:** The WP Leaders along with the project Coordinator should identify as early as possible any barriers to be overcome in order to meet the WP objectives, the activities required to overcome these barriers, the personnel allocations which will provide the right competencies to perform the tasks and the time / budget allocation rules which allow to reach the intermediate objectives.
- **Time risks:** In terms of deadlines, it is important that the project follow the work plan, therefore the WP Leaders together with the Coordinator should identify early in advance any schedule change or delay in producing the expected deliverables and the impact of such a delay on the overall progress of the project; the organisational and budget changes which may be necessary to catch up on delays.

- **Competence risks:** Partners should identify as early as possible the required personnel with the relevant expertise to perform the tasks as well as the possible conflicting demands for the required personnel within each organization.
- **Force majeure risks:** In the case of force majeure, the project Coordinator should identify any risks with the WP Leaders, define mitigation plans according to the EU and project country laws, and communicate that with the Project Officer and Policy Officer (especially in case of political issues).

3.3 Risk management process

All the identified risks are incorporated into a Risk Log File, which is also available online at the Project Management Tool. The risks will be maintained as permanent registers (never deleted) in order to provide a complete, accurate and updated view of all the incurred risks of the project (irrespectively on whether or not they have already been solved).

The risks are duly characterized by:

- Risk number
- Responsible partner (the partner responsible for its resolution and follow-up)
- Description (textual),
- Impact/risk level (high, medium, low)
- Likelihood (unlikely, likely, very likely),
- Situation (inactive, pending, solved),
- Proactive measures
- Action (adopted countermeasures or remedial actions).

Source	Created By	PROBABILITY			IMPACT			Result	IMPACT AREAS			Mitigation/Response Plan	Status
		Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High		Cost	Schedule	Performance		
1 Resistance to institutional change	Vicky M. 13/03/2020			7		5	35			X	Design of a change management strategy and Co-design and participatory approach for the design of GEPs	Pending	
2 Dissemination KPIs do not reach the targets	Vicky M. 13/03/2020		4				32			X	Dissemination and exploitation will be handled by VIL, having long experience in this role and a strategic plan will be behind these Indicators and its targets.	Pending	
3 Difficulties in engagement; low participation in the co-design process	Vicky M. 13/03/2020	3				6	16			X	(a) Trust building measures in order to motivate experts and RPOs/ RFOs staff to participate. All partners have long experience in engagement actions and can adapt the strategy accordingly to possible emerging needs. (b) Contact key experts and other RPOs through pre-existing channels and networks. (c) Achieve maximum engagement results from external stakeholders through the CALIPER Research and Innovation Hub.	Pending	
4 Insufficient participation of audience to raising awareness and stakeholder engagement	Vicky M. 13/03/2020	3				6	18			X	Integrate raising awareness events and stakeholder's engagement with participatory need analysis and co-design activities, in line with civic engagement strategy and activities.	Pending	
5 Changes in the project team	Vicky M. 13/03/2020		6		3		18			X	Identify these changes the soonest possible. Require from partners to include substitutes with equivalent (or higher) qualifications and experience.	Pending	
6 Internal coordination difficulties	Vicky M. 13/03/2020	2				6	12			X	The involvement of a large number of people from different backgrounds may be challenging in terms of coordination and efficient communication but the creation of GEP Working Groups as well as the online training sessions will help to address these difficulties. Continuous liaison between partners and mutual understanding and a problem solving and mutual understanding attitude will be adopted to bridge any differences.	Pending	
A change in upper management results in	Vicky M.										A written binding commitment will be requested by the upper management with a condition that there	Pending	

Figure 1: Screenshot of risk log at the project management tool

3.4 Potential risks

This is the current updated list of risks has already been identified at the Grand Agreement. This list will be further extended as the project progresses.

Nr.	Responsible	WP	Description of risk	Impact level	Likelihood	Situation	Proactive measures	Action
1	ALL	1	Cancellation of the physical meeting for the Capacity Building training, due to force majeure.	Low	Likely	Solved		Training online replaced the physical training. The leader used the appropriate infrastructure and all participants were active.
2	ALL	1	Cancellation of national training meetings due to force majeure	Low	Likely	Pending		Physical meetings will be changed to online.
3	ALL	2	Cancellation of physical meetings (Multi Stakeholder dialogues + meetings of the working group) due to force majeure	Low	Unlikely	Pending		Physical meetings will be changed to online.
4	ALL	2	Delays in performing tasks for WP2 as a consequence of delays in WP1 due to force majeure	Low	Likely	Inactive		To extend period to carry out WP1
5	ULB, STU-BA	2,5	Difficulties in engagement; low participation in the co-design process	Low	likely	inactive	(a) Trust building measures in order to motivate experts and RPOs/ RFOs staff to participate. All partners have long experience in engagement actions and can adapt the strategy accordingly to possible	-

							emerging needs. (b) Contact key experts and other RPOs through pre-existing channels and networks. (c) Achieve maximum engagement results from external stakeholders through the CALIPER Research and Innovation Hub.	
6	UZG	3	Resistance to institutional change	Medium	Very likely	Inactive	Design of a change management strategy and Co-design and participatory approach for the design of GEPs	
7	VIL, STU-BA	5,6	Ongoing dissemination may take more efforts & resources than planned	Low	Likely	Inactive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous on-line liaison between the Partners on their use of resources, • shared dissemination opportunities with other related projects, • previous relevant experience of the Partners, and the project's R&I Hub will make sure that all project results will be diffused to the different channels of stakeholders • Sustainability Plans will be developed by each RPO/RFO 	
8	STU-BA	5	Insufficient participation of audience to raising awareness and	Low	Likely	Inactive	Integrate raising awareness events and stakeholder's engagement with participatory need analysis and co-	

			stakeholder engagement				design activities, in line with civic engagement strategy and activities.	
9	VIL	6	Dissemination KPIs do not reach the targets	Medium	Likely	Inactive	Dissemination and exploitation will be handled by VIL, having long experience in this role and a strategic plan will be behind these Indicators and its targets.	
10	VIL, STU-BA	5,6	Event, workshops, conferences that consortium members should participate/organise cancel due to force majeure	Medium	Likely	Inactive	Consortium members will investigate for online alternative solutions that will have the same impact, e.g. e-discussions, journal articles and book chapters, etc.	
11	VIL	7	Internal coordination difficulties	Low	Unlikely	Inactive		
12	VIL	7	Changes in the project team	Medium	Likely	Inactive		
13	VIL	7	Financial risk	Low	Likely	Inactive	Any uncertainty associated with the project's evolution can pose a significant impact on project costs. For this reason, administrative/financial management will not be limited to reporting but it will also include a close financial monitoring process so as to constantly assess financial progress and be able to identify early signs of concern.	

14	ALL	ALL	Delays to deliver input for other WPs	Medium	Likely	Inactive	Proper planning of work with milestones and alternative plans in case deviations from the plan occur. Continuous communication among WPLs.	
15	ALL	ALL	Data handling: risk to disclose personal and sensitive data	Low	Unlikely	Inactive	Legal and ethical procedures will be prepared including security measures and a Data Management Plan early at the project.	
16	ALL	ALL	A change in upper management results in diminished commitment to the project.	Low	Unlikely	Inactive	A written binding commitment will be requested by the upper management with a condition that there will be a continuation support to GEP whatever change shall happen at the governance/decision making level	
17	ALL	5	Difficulties in active involvement and personal meetings of GEP Working Groups	Medium	Likely	Inactive	Ensure the way of communication within GEP Working groups in each RPOs/ RFOs	
18	ALL	5	Priority of institutions managements will be changed due to coronavirus occurrence and its consequences	Medium	Likely	Inactive	Much bigger personal involvement and effort of project members and WG members in each RPOs/ RFOs will be needed	

Table 13: CALIPER potential risks

Annex I: Peer Review report template

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

Internal Review

Deliverable title
WPx- title

Internal review, Dx.x: Title

Page 2 of 3

Evaluation: Please rate the quality of the deliverable on a scale from 1 to 5. (1:poor, 2:below average, 3:average, 4:good, 5:excellent)

Criterion	Grade	Comment
Technical/Scientific value		
Structure		
Clarity		
Relevance to objectives ¹		

Major strengths and/or weaknesses: (Please explain briefly)

Recommendation:

Deliverable has sufficient quality as is ² :	
Deliverable needs minor re-writing (please specify):	
Deliverable needs major re-writing (please specify):	

Comments & suggestions:

#	Description of proposed change	Importance ³ (E HR R)
1		
2		
3		

¹ The reviewer should consult the description of the respective Work Package, as included in the Technical Annex.

² The current version of the deliverable is ready for submission

³ The reviewer should indicate the significance of the proposed change with regards to the overall quality of the deliverable. Proposed values include: E (essential), HR (Highly Recommended), R (Recommended)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

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Internal review, Dx.x: Title

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Next steps:

Is it necessary for the revised deliverables to be reviewed again before submission?	(Yes/No)
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[Date]

[Reviewer's Name, Organisation, Affiliation]

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